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SURMOUNTING THE INSTRUCTION-RELATED CONSTRAINING INFLUENCE: POSITIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: This study assessed the level of stress that teachers experience under the new normal in identified schools. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the respondents' demographic profile. The data obtained were analyzed using percentage weighted mean, response on the stress provider were treated using test of significant difference. Based on the findings, data shows that working environment have directly contributed to the stress of the teachers and administrators especially work-related stressor. It can also be noted that distribution and retrieval have strong influence on the stress of the teachers. Thus, additional manpower (i.e., non-teaching) has the potential to lessen the existence of stress in the working environment. Findings also showed that teachers and administrators have different copings strategies under this pandemic.

Keywords: Coping Strategies, Stressor, Workplace, Modules

1. Introduction

Schools and teachers are usually very good at thinking about the well-being of their pupils. We consider ourselves to have a duty of care to our learners. We do not usually think about our own well-being until it is too late and we are sick. People who take on caring roles are often not good at looking after themselves. It is vital that we manage our own well-being, as we cannot manage pupils and learning if we cannot manage ourselves. Taking time to manage your stress is essential in order to teach effectively and to help students with their stress around learning (Travers, 2017).

Teachers are key social agents that help learners to dream and reach their highest potential and develop into responsible citizens. However, over the years teaching has become increasingly stressful (Savitha, 2021). Recent study shows that teaching is one of the most stressful occupations in the U.S. High levels of stress are affecting teacher

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health and well-being, causing teacher burnout, lack of engagement, job dissatisfaction, poor performance, and some of the highest turnover rates (Lambert et al., 2019). Further, stress not only has negative consequences for teachers, it also results in lower achievement for students and higher costs for schools. A New York City study showed higher teacher turnover led to lower fourth and fifth grade student achievement in both math and language arts. The cost of teacher turnover is estimated to be over \$7 billion Puryear (Lever et al., 2017).

Too much stress among teachers might lead to poor physical, mental and emotional state of teachers and possibly affect teacher performance, teacher-student relationship and/or consequently, student performance as well (Glazzard & Rose, 2019). It is therefore necessary to quantify stress and identify potential areas of concern, so there can be necessary environment or personal changes to improve stressful situations. It is not undeniable that teacher stress is linked to poor teacher performance and poor student outcomes (Mokh et al., 2021). According to a longitudinal study, elementary school teachers who have greater stress and show more symptoms of depression create classroom environments that are less conducive to learning, which leads to poor (Jennings et al., 2013).

Teaching is widely recognized to be a stressful occupation, characterized by numerous and varied challenges: administrative burdens, long hours, classroom management difficulties, and lack of autonomy, to name but a few. Teachers are isolated from colleagues for much of the day, spending less than 5% of their work time collaborating with peers (Scholastic & the Gates Foundation, 2012). They are also paid less than other workers with similar experience and education, a gap that has grown from 4.3% in 1996 to 17% in 2015, according to the Economic Policy Institute (Allegreto & Mishel, 2016). Further, teachers face significant social and political scrutiny as to how they do their jobs (Goldstein, 2014).

These demands take a toll, resulting in job dissatisfaction, workplace fatigue, burnout, and reduced occupational commitment. The statistics on teacher turnover are grim: Research estimates that between 19% and 30% of new teachers leave the field within the first five years of teaching, which can reduce the esprit de corps of their campus community and negatively affect student learning (Guin, 2004; Kraft & Papay, 2014). In the most recent PDK poll, half of teachers surveyed said they had considered leaving the profession within the last year, with low pay and high stress most frequently cited as the reasons (PDK International, 2019).

In the Philippines, a few numbers of the suicide of teachers provides alarming results in the education sector (BusinessMirror, 2018). Based on several media reports, the Department of Education is mourning over the death of a teacher and say that they will look into it and it is non-work related. The Department also clarifies that the workload should not be blamed for the teacher's suicide because there are other factors that may contribute (Mateo, 2018; Reyes, 2018). While The Teachers' Dignity Coalition (TDC) met with DepEd officials to discuss concerns over the supposed workload, it cited that the heavy burden of paperwork is one among the reasons of the teacher who hanged herself in one case of teachers' suicide in 2018.

While the education sector refuses to correlate workload with the suicides, they still emphasize that it is a wake-up call for public school teachers to learn how to manage work pressures that reacting to news circulating on social media that heavy paperwork had prompted one multi-grade teacher to commit suicide. The Department of Education urged to lighten teacher workloads (Hernando-Malipot, 2018). Due to the numerous reports, the secretary of the Department of Education said that they have already reduced the workload of teachers, which includes clerical and paper works. The

secretary added that they are currently studying how to unload further teachers, based on the news report (Terrazola, 2018). Stress among teachers is always discussed by international and national level but very little research has been carried out in in the local level to establish the sources as well as the impact of this on the teacher performance. Hence, the study proposes what contributes to the perceived stress of the teachers under new normal.

2. Purpose of the Study

This study assessed study assessed the level of stress that teachers experience under the new normal in identified schools. Moreover, it addressed the level of stress in terms of: Workplace, Distribution learning modules, retrieval of learning modules, Safety and health protocols of the schools, Experience during distance learning. The significant difference between respondents' perception on the level of teacher's stress was also treated.

3. Research Methodology

This research used descriptive research method to gather the information about the level of stress of teachers as perceived by the respondent's group in the identified School together with sets of questionnaires as data gathering instruments. The data gathered used processed and analyzed utilizing the appropriate statistical software with 0.05 level of significance. The research started on the orientation of the respondents on current study. The researcher used the INPUT-PROCESS-OUTPUT approach. It also addresses the following level of stress of the teachers in terms of workplace, distribution and retrieval of learning modules, safety and health protocols of the school and experiences during distance learning. The respondents of the study were the identified school in Cebu and Mandaue City using purposive sampling. The questionnaire of the was adopted This was adapted from the study of Randy Ventayen (2021). Distribution and Retrieval of modules and School safety and protocols. This was adapted from the study of Marilyn Olivo (2021). Experiences during distance learning. This was adapted from the study of Klapproth et al., 2020, and lastly coping strategies. This was adapted from the study of Paula Harlow, 2008.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Workplace

Working Place	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
My job has a lot of responsibility, but I don't have very much authority	3.98	A	3.32	A
My workplace environment is not very pleasant or safe	3.57	A	3.46	A
My job often interferes with my family and social obligations, or personal needs	4	A	3.80	A
I tend to have frequent arguments with administrator and co-teachers	3.9	A	3.42	A
Most of the time I feel I have very little control over my life at work	4.05	A	3.18	A
Weighted mean	3.9	A	3.44	A

Table 1 presents the data in terms of Working Place. Data shows that the statement refers to most of the time I feel I have very little control over my life at work

got the highest weighted mean of 4.05 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to, my workplace environment is not very pleasant or safe got the lowest weighted mean of 3.57 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, my job often interferes with my family and social obligations, or personal needs got the highest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to most of the time, I feel I have very little control over my life at work got the lowest weighted mean of 3.18 which verbally described as agree.

Table 2. Distribution of Modules

Distribution of modules	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
The schedule of Learning module distribution suited your available time.	3.48	A	3.80	A
The Distribution of modules was well organized.	4.58	SA	3.62	A
The orientation on the use of module during the distribution was clear.	4.06	A	3.40	A
The school provided us with schedule on when to answer the modules and when to submit.	3.74	A	3.50	A
The school provided us with options on how distribute printed module.	3.74	A	3.64	A
Weighted mean	3.72	A	3.59	A

Table 2 presents the data in terms of Distribution of modules. Data shows that the statement refers to the distribution of modules was well organized got the highest weighted mean of 4.58 which verbally described as strongly agree, while the statement refers to, the schedule of learning module distribution suited your available time. got the lowest weighted mean of 3.48 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, the schedule of learning module distribution suited your available time got the highest weighted mean of 3.80 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to the orientation on the use of module during the distribution was clear got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree.

Table 3. Retrieval of Modules

Retrieval of modules	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
There are available boxes in the school where to submit the modules.	3.77	A	3.40	A
The schedule for retrieval is suited to the availability of the parent	3.48	A	4.00	A
In case the parents could not submit the modules, we were told to just seek the help of the barangay officers	3.9	A	3.82	A
The retrieval of the modules is organized.	3.83	A	3.62	A
The time to retrieve modules is reasonable	3.77	A	3.42	A
Weighted mean	3.75	A	3.65	A

Table 3 presents the data in terms of Retrieval of modules. Data shows that the statement refers to in case the parents could not submit the modules, we were told to just seek the help of the barangay officers got the highest weighted mean of 3.9 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to, the schedule for retrieval is suited to the availability of the parent got the lowest weighted mean of 3.48 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, the schedule for retrieval is suited to the availability of the parent got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to there are available boxes in the school where to submit the modules. got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree.

Table 4. Health and Safety

Health and Safety	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
School is clean and well-maintained.	3.70	A	3.46	A
School has safety equipment like handwashing area, foot press alcohol dispenser, thermal scanner and disinfecting mat	3.48	A	3.82	A
School has printed arrows use to observe physical distancing	3.80	A	3.42	A
School has assigned Purok Parent Leaders per grade level to get the modules maintain minimal number of parents inside the school.	3.28	A	3.42	A
Teachers and Parents wear face mask and face shield while inside the school premises	3.70	A	3.22	A
Weighted mean	3.72	A	3.57	A

Table 4 presents the data in terms of Health and Safety. Data shows that the statement refers to school has printed arrows use to observe physical distancing got the highest weighted mean of 3.80 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to, school has assigned Purok Parent Leaders per grade level to get the modules maintain minimal number of parents inside the school got the lowest weighted mean of 3.28 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, school has safety equipment like hand washing area, foot press alcohol dispenser, thermal scanner and disinfecting mat got the highest weighted mean of 3.82 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to teachers and parents wear face mask and face shield while inside the school premises got the lowest weighted mean of 3.22 which verbally described as agree.

Table 5. Experience during Distance Learning

Experience during Distance Learning	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Excessive workload for teachers	3.53	A	3.40	A
Low housing conditions	3.46	A	3.40	A
Access to computer hardware and software	3.90	A	3.56	A
Internet connectivity	3.80	A	3.40	A
Socialization	3.73	A	3.60	A
Weighted mean	3.684	A	3.472	A

Table 5 presents the data in terms of Health and Safety. Data shows that the statement refers access to computer hardware and software got the highest weighted

mean of 3.90 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to, low housing conditions got the lowest weighted mean of 3.46 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, socialization got the highest weighted mean of 3.60 which verbally described as agree, while the statements refer to excessive workload for teachers, low housing conditions, and internet connectivity got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree.

Table 6. Coping Strategies

Coping Strategies	Teachers		Administrators	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I've been concentrating my efforts on doing something about the situation I'm in.	3.56	A	3.52	A
I've been taking action to try to make the situation better.	3.42	A	3.52	A
I've been taking action to try to make the situation better.	3.65	A	3.40	A
I've been thinking hard about what steps to take.	3.46	A	3.62	A
I've been trying to see it in a different light, to make it seem more positive.	3.23	A	3.60	A
Weighted mean	3.464	A	3.532	A

Table 6 presents the data in terms of Coping Strategies. Data shows that the statement refers I've been taking action to try to make the situation better. got the highest weighted mean of 3.65 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to, I've been trying to see it in a different light, to make it seem more positive got the lowest weighted mean of 3.23 which verbally described as agree. While administrators on the other hand, I've been thinking hard about what steps to take got the highest weighted mean of 3.62 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to, I've been taking action to try to make the situation better got the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 which verbally described as agree.

Table 7. Significant Mean Difference Between Respondent Group

Sources	constructs	MEAN	p-value	Decision
Teachers		3.9	0.008595	Not Significant
Administrators	Workplace	3.44		
	Distribution	3.92 2.59	0.16305	Significant
	Retrieval	3.75 3.652	0.49472	Significant
	Healthy and Safety	3.592 3.468	0.76449	Significant
	Experience in Distance Learning	3.68 3.47	0.064441	Not significant

Table 7 presents the significant difference of the respondent groups perception on the level of stressor. Finding shows that majority of the constructs were significant, Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Although, workplace and experience in distance learning were rated not significant means no difference were seen. This indicates that respondents have the same experiences in the workplace and in distance learning.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings, data shows that working environment have directly contributed to the stress of the teachers and administrators especially work-related stressor. It can also be noted that distribution and retrieval have strong influence on the stress of the teachers. Thus, additional manpower (i.e., non-teaching) has the potential to lessen the existence of stress in the working environment. Findings also showed that teachers and administrators have different copings strategies under this pandemic

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